

ONE BIG PROBLEM IN MY EDUCATION – AND HOW TO FIX IT

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Abstract. *This research aims to explore the problems which were held in educational places such as school, universities. Many students want to study in a modernized schools while they are living in a technologies developed world. I have learned about the foreign education system through my own experiences and I want to apply it in ours. Some of the problems in education are very relevant for students studying in Uzbekistan, in particular at Termez State University. One of the biggest problems is the lack of modern technologies and the insufficiently formed close, friendly relations between teachers and students. However, this issue is not merely institutional — it is also cultural and psychological, shaped by long-standing traditions and societal expectations.*

Keywords: *Methods, teaching style, structure, new techniques, learning process, traditional methods, modern technologies, networking.*

Many students, including myself, often feel hesitant to express my thoughts freely in academic settings. This hesitation does not stem from a lack of knowledge or ability, but from a mindset deeply ingrained in us from early childhood. Uzbek people always try to control someone, they want to make everything perfectly but they don't mostly start from themselves. If we want to change the society we should change ourselves firstly then others will be more easier. "Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world"¹. In my culture, children are often taught to obey, remain silent, and not give question authority. Even lullabies and traditional parenting encourage conformity and quiet behavior. As a result, students grow up being cautious, passive, and afraid of expressing their opinions, especially in formal settings like universities, in front of public because of childhood trauma. Elder people are asking after we grow up why you are not giving your opinion, say something and that time it will be late for kid. "The only thing that interferes with my learning is my education."²

This mentality persists into higher education, where classroom environments often lack active dialogue. Many students refrain from asking questions during lectures, fearing they might be judged or misunderstood. Even at university I faced that many teachers say know your position, who are you, why you are texting to me after class, why you are speaking loud to me. Likewise, professors may not create a space that encourages interaction or discussion. "Teachers need not only content knowledge, but also pedagogical content knowledge to be effective."³ Lessons are mostly lecture-based, and technology is rarely used to enhance engagement or creativity. "Despite high enrollment in schools, learning outcomes remain low in many countries."⁴

As a 3rd year student university, I was fortunate to participate in international exchange programs. I studied for one semester in China twice, and once in Malaysia.

¹ Nelson Mandela, Long Walk to Freedom, 1994

² Albert Einstein, quoted in Education and the Significance of Life by Jiddu Krishnamurti, 1953.

³ Shulman, L. S. (1986). "Those who understand: Knowledge growth in teaching." Educational Researcher, 15(2), 4–14.

⁴ World Bank (2018). World Development Report: Learning to Realize Education's Promise.

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Luckily, my classmates are all from overseas, like Mexica, Italy, Elbador, Germany, Indonesa and else. These experiences broadened my perspective and gave me firsthand insight into how advanced and student-centered their educational systems are. "Education should not just teach us how to make a living, it should teach us how to live."⁵

Each day I send my free time to learn about new methods, asked from friends about their sytems. In both countries, education starts with meaningful activities from early childhood. In kindergartens, children engage in hands-on activities like cooking, building model structures, playing musical instruments, participating in sports, and practicing public speaking. These methods not only develop practical skills but also boost confidence and independent thinking from a young age.

During school years, students take weekly tests in each subject. The student who scores the highest becomes the teacher's assistant for that subject, which changes weekly. This encourages healthy competition and motivates students to study harder. In addition, parents are actively involved — they drop off and pick up their children daily and communicate directly with teachers to monitor academic progress and behavioral changes.

My experience at a university in China further highlighted the benefits of a modern educational environment. Every classroom was equipped with electronic boards and projectors, and lessons regularly included PowerPoint slides and video materials. There was a strong emphasis on the relationship between students and professors — friendly, respectful, and collaborative.

Most impressive was the use of a digital learning platform called UMU. It was central to classroom activities. Each subject had specific sections on the platform, where students submitted assignments, uploaded notes, completed quizzes, and participated in discussions. The system automatically calculated grades based on performance.

What makes UMU unique is its dynamic design:

1. Lesson Notes – Students upload photos of notes taken during class, proving they are engaged and reflective.
2. Daily Tests – Short quizzes are conducted after every lesson to reinforce understanding.
3. Homework Assignments – All tasks are submitted through UMU with clear grading rubrics.
4. Group Projects – For example, in literature classes, students perform and record scenes from plays using university-provided equipment.
5. Library Use – Borrowing books from the library contributes to students' academic score.

Class participation is also crucial. When a professor asks a question, students are divided into groups to discuss. Then, one group is randomly selected to present their ideas. This method keeps all students alert, engaged, and accountable throughout the lesson.

Even the grading system reflects this level of precision and motivation. To pass a course, students must score over 110% by accumulating points from attendance, classwork, group activities, and UMU submissions. If a student scores below this benchmark, they fail and must retake the course the following year.

⁵ Dewey, J. (1938). Experience and Education.

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This strict but fair approach ensures continuous effort and consistent learning. "Technology integration remains superficial in many classrooms, lacking depth in cognitive engagement."⁶

Another aspect that impressed me abroad was the well-structured daily schedule and financial support system provided to students. Classes are held from morning until evening, ensuring that students remain fully immersed in their academic environment. To support this intensive learning routine, students receive a sufficient monthly stipend from the university. This financial assistance allows them to focus entirely on their studies without the need to seek part-time jobs or extra tutoring.

Moreover, there is little need for additional private lessons because the university's teaching staff are highly qualified professionals, many of whom have studied or trained abroad. These instructors have international experience and excellent teaching methodologies. They can explain complex topics in a simple and accessible way, making the classroom experience both efficient and enriching.

As a result, students receive all the knowledge and guidance they need directly from their professors during regular class hours. This reduces stress, saves time, and builds trust in the formal education system. It also levels the playing field — students from different economic backgrounds all have equal access to quality education without having to pay extra.

In conclusion, my experiences abroad showed me how much potential we have to improve our education system back home. By integrating modern technology, encouraging active learning, and reshaping our cultural approach to education, we can build a generation of confident, capable, and creative students. Reforming education is not only about changing tools — it's about transforming minds.

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